

On k -Equivalence Domination in Graphs

S. Arumugam^{1,2} and M. Sundarakannan¹

¹. National Centre for Advanced Research in Discrete Mathematics, Kalasalingam University
Anand Nagar, Krishnankoil-626126, INDIA.

². School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, The University of Newcastle
NSW 2308, Australia.

Email: s.arumugam.klu@gmail.com, m.sundarakannan@gmail.com

Abstract: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. A subset S of V is called an *equivalence set* if every component of the induced subgraph $\langle S \rangle$ is complete. If further at least one component of $\langle V - S \rangle$ is not complete, then S is called a Smarandachely equivalence set. Let k be any nonnegative integer. An equivalence set $S \subseteq V$ is called a *k -equivalence set* if $\Delta(\langle S \rangle) \leq k$. A k -equivalence set which dominates G is called a *k -equivalence dominating set* of G . In this paper we introduce some parameters using the just defined notion and discuss their relations with other graph theoretic parameters.

Key Words: Domination, irredundance, Smarandachely equivalence set, k -equivalence set, k -equivalence domination, k -equivalence irredundance.

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In this paper we consider only finite undirected simple graphs. For graph theoretic terminology we rely on [5]. Throughout this article, let G be a graph with vertex set V and edge set E .

One of the dominant areas in graph theory is the study of domination and related notions such as independence, irredundance, covering and matching. (In this connection see [9-10].)

Let $v \in V$. The open neighbourhood of v denoted by $N(v)$ and the closed neighbourhood of v denoted by $N[v]$ are defined by $N(v) = \{u \in V : uv \in E\}$ and $N[v] = N(v) \cup \{v\}$. A subset S of V is said to be an *independent set* if no two vertices in S are adjacent. A subset S of V is called a *dominating set* of G if every vertex in $V - S$ is adjacent to at least one vertex in S . The cardinality of a minimum dominating set is called the *domination number* and it is denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

There are many variations of domination in graphs. In the book by Haynes et al. [9] it is proposed that a type of domination is “fundamental” if every connected nontrivial graph has a dominating set of this type and this type of dominating set S is defined in terms of some “natural” property of the subgraph induced by S . Examples include total domination, independent domination, connected domination and paired domination. In this paper we introduce

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the concept of k -equivalence domination, which is a fundamental concept in the above sense.

An *equivalence graph* is a vertex disjoint union of complete graphs. An *equivalence covering* of a G is a family of equivalence subgraphs of G such that every edge of G is an edge of at least one member of the family. The *equivalence covering number* of G is the cardinality of a minimum equivalence covering of G . The equivalence covering number was first studied in [6]. Interesting bounds for the equivalence covering number in terms of maximal degree of the complement were obtained in [2]. The computation of the equivalence covering number of split graphs was considered in [4].

An important concept which uses equivalence graph is subcoloring studied in [1,8,11]. A *subcoloring* of G is a partition of its vertex set into subsets X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k , where for each $i \leq k$ the induced subgraph $\langle X_i \rangle$ is an equivalence graph. The order of a minimum subcoloring is called the *subchromatic number* of G . The notion of subchromatic number is a natural generalization of the well studied chromatic number since for any independent set S , the induced subgraph $\langle S \rangle$ is trivially an equivalence graph.

The concept of equivalence graph also arises naturally in the study of domination in claw-free graphs, as shown by the following theorem proved in [7].

Theorem 1 ([7]) *Any minimal dominating set of a $K_{1,3}$ -free graph is a collection of disjoint complete subgraphs.*

Motivated by these observations, we have introduced the concept of equivalence set and equivalence domination number in [3].

Definition 2 *A subset S of V is called an equivalence set if every component of the induced subgraph $\langle S \rangle$ is complete. A dominating set of G which is also an equivalence set is called an equivalence dominating set of G . The equivalence domination number $\gamma_e(G)$ is defined to be the cardinality of a minimum equivalence dominating set of G . An equivalence set S is called a Smarandachely equivalence set if at least one component of $\langle V - S \rangle$ is not complete.*

In this paper we introduce the concept of k -equivalence set and several parameters using this concept and investigate their relation with the six basic parameters of the domination chain. (For details see [9, §3.5].)

Definition 3 *Let k be any nonnegative integer. A subset S of V is called a k -equivalence set if every component of the induced subgraph $\langle S \rangle$ is complete—i.e., if S is an equivalence set of G —and $\Delta(\langle S \rangle) \leq k$.*

The concept of k -equivalence set is a natural generalization of the concept of independence, since every independent set is obviously 0-equivalence set. Also every $(k - 1)$ -equivalence set is a k -equivalence set and k -equivalence is a hereditary property. Hence a k -equivalence set S is a maximal k -equivalence set if and only if $S \cup \{v\}$ is not a k -equivalence set for all $v \in V - S$. Thus a k -equivalence set $S \subseteq V$ is maximal if and only if for every $v \in V - S$, there exists a clique C in $\langle S \rangle$ such that v is adjacent to a vertex in C and v is not adjacent to a vertex in C or there exist two cliques C_1 and C_2 in $\langle S \rangle$ such that v is adjacent to a vertex in C_1 and to

a vertex in C_2 or there exists a clique C in $\langle S \rangle$ such that $|C| = k + 1$ and v is adjacent to all vertices in C .

Definition 4 The k -equivalence number $\beta_e^k(G)$ and the lower k -equivalence number $i_e^k(G)$ are defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_e^k(G) &= \max\{|S| : S \text{ is a maximal } k\text{-equivalence set of } G\} \text{ and} \\ i_e^k(G) &= \min\{|S| : S \text{ is a maximal } k\text{-equivalence set of } G\}.\end{aligned}$$

Clearly $i_e^k(G) \leq \beta_e^k(G)$ and $\beta_0(G) \leq \beta_e^k(G)$.

Definition 5 A dominating set S of V which is also a k -equivalence set is called a k -equivalence dominating set of G . The k -equivalence domination number $\gamma_e^k(G)$ and the upper k -equivalence domination number $\Gamma_e^k(G)$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_e^k(G) &= \min\{|S| : S \text{ is a minimal } k\text{-equivalence dominating set of } G\} \text{ and} \\ \Gamma_e^k(G) &= \max\{|S| : S \text{ is a minimal } k\text{-equivalence dominating set of } G\}.\end{aligned}$$

Since every maximal k -equivalence set is a dominating set of G and every maximal independent set is a minimal k -equivalence dominating set, the parameters $\gamma_e^k(G)$ and $\Gamma_e^k(G)$ fit into the domination chain, thus leading to the following extended domination chain: $ir(G) \leq \gamma(G) \leq \gamma_e^k(G) \leq i(G) \leq \beta_0(G) \leq \beta_e^k(G) \leq \Gamma(G) \leq IR(G)$.

Definition 6 An irredundant set which is also a k -equivalence set is called a k -equivalence irredundant set. The k -equivalence irredundance number $ir_e^k(G)$ and the upper k -equivalence irredundance number $IR_e^k(G)$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned}ir_e^k(G) &= \min\{|I| : I \text{ is a maximal } k\text{-equivalence irredundant set of } G\} \text{ and} \\ IR_e^k(G) &= \max\{|I| : I \text{ is a maximal } k\text{-equivalence irredundant set of } G\}.\end{aligned}$$

Remark 7 Let S be a minimal k -equivalence dominating set of G . Since S is a minimal dominating set, it is a maximal irredundant set. Thus S is a maximal k -equivalence irredundant set of G . Thus we have the following: Any minimal k -equivalence dominating set is a maximal k -equivalence irredundant set.

For any G , we have $ir_e^k(G) \leq \gamma_e^k(G) \leq \Gamma_e^k(G) \leq IR_e^k(G)$ and $ir_e^k(G) \leq \gamma_e^k(G) \leq i_e^k(G) \leq \beta_e^k(G)$.

Lemma 8 If D is a minimal k -equivalence dominating set of G , then D is both a minimal dominating set and a minimal $(k + 1)$ -equivalence dominating set of G .

Proof Assume that D is a minimal k -equivalence dominating set of G , and let $x \in D$. Then $D - \{x\}$ is not a k -equivalence dominating set and $\Delta(\langle D - \{x\} \rangle) \leq \Delta(\langle D \rangle) \leq k$. Therefore D is a minimal dominating set of G and D is a $(k + 1)$ -equivalence set. \square

Corollary 9 For every nonnegative integer k , $\gamma_e^{k+1}(G) \leq \gamma_e^k(G)$ and $\Gamma_e^k(G) \leq \Gamma_e^{k+1}(G)$.

The proof of the next result is similar to that of Theorem 3.2 in [3].

Theorem 10 For any graph G , $\gamma(G) \leq 2ir_e^k(G)$.

Proof Let $I = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k\}$ be an ir_e^k -set of G . Let y_i be a private neighbor of x_i with respect to I and let $A = I \cup \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\}$. If there exists a vertex x in $V - A$ such that $N(x) \cap (V - A) = \emptyset$, then $B = I \cup \{x\}$ is a k -equivalence set of G and x is an isolated vertex in $\langle B \rangle$. Further for each i , y_i is a private neighbor of x_i with respect to B ; therefore B is a k -equivalence irredundant set — a contradiction. Whence A is a dominating set of G ; therefore $\gamma(G) \leq 2ir_e^k(G)$. \square

Let k be any integer ≥ 2 . Consider the graphs H_1, H_2 displayed in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively. Obviously $ir_e^k(H_1) = 4$ and $\gamma(H_1) = 5$. Since $\{a, b, c\}$ is a maximal equivalence irredundant set in H_2 , $ir_e^k(H_2) = 3$. Since $\{a, e, f, g\}$ is a maximal irredundant set in H_2 , $ir(H_2) = 4$. Now for the graph $H_3 = P_3 \circ 2K_1$, we have $ir(H_3) = 3$, $ir_e^k(H_3) \geq 4$ and $\gamma(H_3) = 3$. From these information, it is clear that the parameters ir and ir_e^k and the parameters γ and ir_e^k are not comparable. It is not difficult to show that the just mentioned statement holds when $k \leq 1$.

Figure 1 Figure 2

For the complete bipartite graph $H_4 = K_{2,r}, r \geq 3$, we have $i_e^k(H_4) = 2$ and $\beta_0(H_4) = \Gamma_e^k(H_4) = \Gamma(H_4) = IR_e^k(H_4) = \beta_e^k(H_4) = r$. Also $i_e^k(K_n) = \beta_e^k(K_n) = k + 1 \leq n$ whereas $i(K_n) = \beta_0(K_n) = \Gamma_e^k(K_n) = \Gamma(K_n) = IR_e^k(K_n) = IR(K_n) = 1$. Further $i(K_n \circ 2K_1) = 2n - 1$ and $i_e^k(K_n \circ 2K_1) = 2n - (k + 1)$. Hence i_e is not comparable with any of $IR, IR_e^k, \Gamma, \Gamma_e^k, i(G)$ and β_0 . For the graph H_5 obtained from $K_{4,4,4} \circ K_1$, by adding edges in such a way that the subgraph induced by the set of all pendant vertices of the latter is a cycle, we have $\Gamma(H_5) = IR(H_5) = 12$ and $\beta_e^k(H_5) < 12$. Thus β_e^k is not comparable with IR and Γ .

Let H_6 be the graph obtained from the path $P_6 := (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6)$ and the complete graph K_6 with $V(K_6) = \{b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5, b_6\}$ by adding the edges $a_1b_1, a_2b_2, a_4b_4, a_5b_5$ and a_6b_6 . At least one vertex of $V(K_6)$ belongs to every dominating set of H_6 whence $\Gamma(H_6) = 4$. Since $\{b_1, b_2, b_4, b_5, b_6\}$ is an equivalence irredundant set of H_6 , $IR_e^k(H_6) > \Gamma(H_6)$, when $k \geq 4$. It is not difficult to show that the just mentioned statement holds when $k \leq 3$. Also for the graph $H_7 = C_5 \square K_2$, we have $\Gamma(H_7) = 5$ and $IR_e^k(H_7) = 4$. Thus Γ and IR_e^k are not comparable.

The following Hasse diagram summarizes the relationship between the various parameters for the graph G .

Figure 3. Relationship between parameters

Remark 11 It is easy to show that $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq i(G) \leq |V(G)| - \Delta(G)$.

Proposition 12 If G is connected, then

$$\gamma_e^k(G) \leq n - \left\lfloor \frac{2(\text{diam}(G) + 1)}{3} \right\rfloor.$$

Proof Consider an arbitrary induced path P of length $\text{diam}(G)$ in a connected graph G . Every interior vertex in diametrical path dominates at least 3 vertices in G and also there exists maximal k -equivalence set in $\langle V - P \rangle$. Therefore

$$\gamma_e^k(G) \leq n - (\text{diam}(G) + 1) + \left\lfloor \frac{\text{diam}(G) + 1}{3} \right\rfloor = n - \left\lfloor \frac{2}{3}(\text{diam}(G) + 1) \right\rfloor.$$

Also this bound is sharp when $G \cong P_n$, where $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$. □

Theorem 13 If $\Delta(G) \geq 3$ and k is an integer such that $0 \leq k \leq \Delta - 3$, then $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq (\Delta - k - 1)\gamma_e(G) - (k + 1)(\Delta - k - 2)$.

Proof Let D be a γ_e -set of G . If D is k -equivalence set, then $\gamma_e^k(G) = \gamma_e(G)$. Assume $\Delta(\langle D \rangle) \geq k + 1$. Let $x \in D$ such that $\deg_{\langle D \rangle}(x) \geq k + 1$ and let $Q = N(x) \cap (V - D)$. Let P be the set of all private neighbors of x with respect to D . Clearly $P \neq \emptyset$. Let R be a minimum k -equivalence dominating set of $\langle P \rangle$ and let $D' = (D - \{x\}) \cup R$. Now $|R| \leq |Q| \leq \Delta - (k + 1)$. It follows that the set D' is an equivalence dominating set of G and $\langle D' \rangle$ has fewer vertices of degree at least $k + 1$ than $\langle D \rangle$. Let E be a minimal equivalence dominating set of G such that $E \subseteq D'$. Then

$$|E| \leq |D'| = |D| - 1 + |R| = \gamma_e(G) - 1 + |R| \leq \gamma_e(G) + \Delta - k - 2.$$

Continue to repeat the above process until no more vertices of degree larger than k exist

in the resultant set. (Note that the number of such repetitions is at most $|D| - (k + 1)$.) Hence

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_e^k(G) &\leq |D| \leq \gamma_e(G) + (|D| - (k + 1))(\Delta - k - 2) \\ &= (\Delta - k - 1)\gamma_e(G) - (k + 1)(\Delta - k - 2).\end{aligned}$$

The above bound is attained when $G = K_3 \circ 2K_1$. Here $\gamma_e(G) = \gamma_e^2(G) = 3, \gamma_e^1(G) = 4$. \square

Theorem 14 *If k is an integer such that $0 \leq k \leq \omega - 3$, then $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq \left(\frac{\omega-k}{2}\right) \gamma_e^{k+1}(G)$.*

Proof Let D be a γ_e^{k+1} -set of G . If D is k -equivalence set, then $\gamma_e^k(G) = \gamma_e^{k+1}(G)$. Let k be any nonnegative integer not more than $\omega - 3$. Suppose D is not a k -equivalence set. Let X be a subset of D such that for all x , $\deg_{\langle D \rangle}(x) = k + 1$ and let Y be a minimum independent set of $\langle X \rangle$. Since every vertex of $X - Y$ has at least one of its $(k + 1)$ neighbors in Y , $D - Y$ is a k -equivalence set. Note that there are $|Y|(k + 1)$ edges between Y and $D - Y$. Since D is $(k + 1)$ -equivalence set, $|Y|(k + 1) \leq |D - Y|(k + 1)$. Thus $|Y| \leq \frac{1}{2}|D|$.

Let P be the set of all private neighbors of Y with respect to D and R be a minimum k -equivalence dominating set of $\langle P \rangle$. Then R dominates P and $D - Y$ dominates $V - P$. Therefore $R \cup (D - Y)$ is a k -equivalence dominating set and there are no edges between $D - Y$ and R . Since $|R| \leq |P| \leq |Y|(\omega - k - 1)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_e^k(G) &\leq |D| - |Y| + |R| \leq |D| - |Y| + |Y|(\omega - k - 1) = |D| + |Y|(\omega - k - 2) \\ &\leq |D| + \frac{|D|}{2}(\omega - k - 2) = \left(\frac{\omega - k}{2}\right) \gamma_e^{k+1}(G).\end{aligned}$$

\square

Theorem 15 *If $\gamma_e^k(G) \geq 2$, then $m \leq \lfloor \frac{1}{2}(n - \gamma_e^k(G))(n - \gamma_e^k(G) + 2) \rfloor$, where n and m are respectively, the order and the size of the graph G .*

Proof We prove this result by induction on number of vertices. We can assume that $n > 2$ for otherwise the proof is obvious; we can also assume that the result holds for any graph whose order is less than n . If $\gamma_e^k(G) = 2$, then also the conclusion holds. So assume that $\gamma_e^k(G) \geq 3$. Let $v \in V(G)$ with $\deg(v) = \Delta(G)$. Then by Remark 11, $|N(v)| = \Delta(G) \leq n - \gamma_e^k(G)$; i.e., $\Delta(G) = n - \gamma_e^k(G) - r$ where $0 \leq r \leq n - \gamma_e^k(G)$. Let $S = V - N[v]$. Then $|S| = \gamma_e^k(G) + r - 1$. If $u \in N(v)$, then $(S - N(u)) \cup \{u, v\}$ is a dominating set of G and $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq |S - N(u)| + 2$. Thus $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq \gamma_e^k(G) + r - 1 - |S \cap N(u)| + 2$ and so $|S \cap N(u)| \leq r + 1$ for all $u \in N(v)$. Hence the number of edges between $N(v)$ and S , say ℓ_1 , is at most $\Delta(G)(r + 1)$.

Further, if D is a γ_e^k -set of $\langle S \rangle$, then $D \cup \{v\}$ is a k -equivalence dominating set of G . Hence $\gamma_e^k(G) \leq |D \cup \{v\}|$, implying that $\gamma_e^k(\langle S \rangle) \geq \gamma_e^k(G) - 1 \geq 2$. Let ℓ_2 be the size of $\langle S \rangle$. By the inductive hypothesis,

$$\begin{aligned}\ell_2 &\leq \left\lfloor \frac{1}{2}(|S| - \gamma_e^k(\langle S \rangle))(|S| - \gamma_e^k(\langle S \rangle) + 2) \right\rfloor \\ &\leq \left\lfloor \frac{1}{2}(\gamma_e^k(G) + r - 1 - \gamma_e^k(G) + 1)(\gamma_e^k(G) + r - 1 - \gamma_e^k(G) + 1 + 2) \right\rfloor \\ &= \frac{1}{2}r(r + 2).\end{aligned}$$

Let $\ell_3 = |E \langle N[v] \rangle|$. Note that for each u in $N(v)$ there are at most $r + 1$ vertices in S which are adjacent to u . Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |E| &= \ell_1 + \ell_2 + \ell_3 \\ &\leq \Delta(G) \cdot (r + 1) + \frac{1}{2}r \cdot (r + 2) + \Delta(G) + \frac{1}{2}\Delta(G)(\Delta(G) - r - 2) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(n - \gamma_e^k(G))(n - \gamma_e^k(G) + 2) - \frac{1}{2}\Delta(G)(n - \gamma_e^k(G) - \Delta(G)) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}(n - \gamma_e^k(G))(n - \gamma_e^k(G) + 2). \end{aligned}$$

□

Concluding Remarks

We have proved that the decision problem corresponding to the parameters γ_e and Γ_e are NP-complete in [3]. Therefore the computations of γ_e^k and Γ_e^k are also NP-complete. The problem of designing efficient algorithms for computing the parameters in connection with a notion of k -equivalence for special classes of graphs is an interesting direction for further research. In particular one can attempt the design of such algorithms for families of graphs with bounded tree-width.

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